

WORKSHOP ETHICS: SELECTION AND HANDLING OF LABORATORY/WORKSHOP EQUIPMENT/TOOLS-A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This paper was articulated and information generated from relevant literature and reviewed works on the subject matter and gives the definitions of workshop, ethics and other keywords relating them and stipulating the functions of the workshop and the basic tools found in an agricultural mechanization workshop. Tool work habits and work ethics to be followed by the technician were discussed in some details including safe handling of tools, safety of the tools, tool maintenance and repair. Personnel and equipment safety and their guidelines for use were highlighted. Some of the different personnel safety equipment were discussed in some details. The information contained herein is presented in diagrammatic, tabular and textual format and will be beneficial to workshop technicians/technologists as well as the engineers supervising them. The main objective of the work is geared towards highlighting the safety issues in a standard agricultural engineering workshop and how to adhere to them to avoid workshop accidents and maintain a safe workshop environment.

KEYWORDS: Workshop, work ethics, tool work habits, human and tool safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper on work ethics is meant to discuss what we are morally obligated to do in our workshops and laboratories to actualize the purpose for which they were established. It is important to understand what workshops/laboratories are and why they are established in order to utilize them appropriately, and safely. It has been said that there are different tools/equipment useable in different workshops/laboratories for different purposes. Thus there is the need to select them appropriately. The selection, in terms of size and purpose, is very important for the safety of the user, the tool/equipment and the workshop environment. Improper tool/equipment and wrong use of same could be hazardous, thus the import of this review. To commence the review, it is necessary to define the key terms to be discussed in this work.

2. DEFINITION OF TERMS

This section presents some definitions of the key words and terms used in this paper: workshop, ethics, laboratory, equipment/tool, workshop safety signs and signals to give insight on the general focus of the discussion.

2.1 A **workshop** may be a room, rooms or building which provides both the area and tools (or machinery) that may be required for the manufacture or repair of manufactured goods. It could also be a small establishment where manufacturing or handicrafts are carried on. Workshops typically contain workbenches, hand tools, power tools and other hardware. Along with their practical applications for repair of goods or do small manufacturing runs, workshops are used to tinker and make prototypes (Burress, 1997; Carlson, 2013; Flaherty, 2012).

Workshop may also mean a seminar, discussion group, a class or series of classes in which a small group of people learn the methods and skills used in doing something that emphasizes exchange of ideas and the demonstration and application of techniques, skills, etc. Matheney (2018) gave the following workspace per worker: open space workstation – (5.574 – 10.219 m²); workshop group area – 7.432 – 9.290 m²). For mechanical workshop the following dimensions are required in m²: woodshop (11.6) (CTW, 2017); machine shop (500); surveying (94); fabrication and welding (48) etc.

2.2 Ethics are the moral principles that govern a person's behavior or the conducting of an activity. It involves systematizing, defending, and recommending concepts of right and wrong conduct. Of the three major areas of study within ethics recognized today: meta-ethics concerning the theoretical meaning and reference of moral propositions, and how their truth values (if any) can be determined; normative ethics, concerning the practical means of determining a moral course of action; and applied ethics, concerning what a person is obligated (or permitted) to do in a specific situation or a particular domain of action (Bartneck et al., 2021), we, in this paper, are to discuss applied ethics as it concerns the workshop and the laboratory.

2.3 A laboratory (colloquially called lab) is a facility that provides controlled conditions in which scientific or technological research, experiments, and measurements may be performed. Laboratory services are provided in a variety of settings: physicians' offices, clinics, hospitals, and regional and national referral centers (Bertholf, 2017), educational institutions as departmental or subject laboratories, centers of research, etc. Labs are classified based on the type of materials and contaminants handled and the hazards posed. Laboratory classifications can be further broken down by industry – Clinical/Biological, Animal, Chemical, Physical/R & D, etc. Their space requirements range from 10 – 500m² depending on the numbers of equipment and people required.

2.4 Equipment/tool is the set of articles or physical resources serving to equip a person or thing: such as the machinery, tools, etc. that are needed to do a job or the implements used in an operation or activity or needed for a special purpose. A tool is a device for doing work: an object designed to do a specific kind of work such as cutting or chopping by directing manually applied force or by means of a motor. It could be something used in the course of somebody's everyday work or job or the cutting part of machine: the cutting or shaping part of a power-driven device, e.g. the blade on a lathe. Different jobs require different kinds of equipment and tools (Nahmias and Olsen, 2015). Examples of equipment include devices, machines, tools, vehicles, etc.

2.5 Workshop Safety Signs and Signals. Workshop safety signs and signals refer to specific activities, objects or situations providing information or instructions about safety at the workplace, workshop or laboratory by means of a signboard, a safety color, an illuminated sign, an acoustic signal, a verbal communication or a hand signal (HMSO, 1996). These signs are essentially grouped into: prohibitive signs (do not do i.e. prohibiting behavior), warning signs (caution, danger), mandatory signs (must do i.e. action to be followed), safe condition signs (safest way to go, emergency exit/escape route, first aid) and firefighting signs (indicating fire equipment) as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Safety signs (HMSO, 1996)

2.6 Tool Work Habit. A good set of tools is your most important possession and no matter how fancy your tools are, they won't look after themselves. It's important to treat them like anything else you love - with care and attention (AMI, 2020). How and where you store them, and how you clean and re-store them after use defines tool work habit.

2.7 Work Ethics is one of these qualities that usually get over looked because of which people fail to understand its importance and how it can help one become valuable asset in the work place. Strong work ethics is an encapsulation of various qualities like professionalism, punctuality, loyalty, integrity, dedication, discipline, motivation, etc. (Gopakumar, 2020).

3. SELECTION OF TOOLS/EQUIPMENT

This is one of the foremost functions of effective workshop ethics as it determines the workability of the job to be done in terms of speed and efficiency. A great job may fail to be executable if the most appropriate tools/equipment combinations are not available. So it is vital to know what the best tools/equipment for a particular job is. Tool/equipment is designed to make a job easier and enable one to work more efficiently. If they are not properly selected, used and cared for, their advantages and benefits are lost. Regardless of the type of work to be done, one must have to choose/select and use the correct tools in order to do the assigned work quickly, accurately, and safely. Without the proper tools and the knowledge of how to use them, time is wasted, efficiency is reduced, and even injury may be sustained (Maaswinkel and Offereins, 1990). Finally, tools and equipment need regular maintenance, requiring good workshop facilities, a reliable supply of spare parts as well as qualified technical staff. The staff must know how to use the tools and how to operate the equipment in order to secure good work progress and the expected high quality results. It is also important that staff know the full potential, as well as the limitation, of the use of manual and work methods based on the equipment. This underscores

the fact that tools and equipment require trained operators and supervisory staff who are proficient in their operation and maintenance. Since each job requires its set of tools/equipment and each specific workshop/laboratory should be serviced by specialized equipment/tools, it will be difficult to enumerate all the tools/equipment here. Suffice it to say that each trained technical staff in any workshop/laboratory should be able to properly choose and select his/her tools/equipment for any assigned job. Part of workshop ethics is the ability to properly select/choose the tool or the set of tools for a specified assignment (Fred's Appliance Academy, 2017).

According to True Value (2020), tools are particularly important in the workshop/laboratory. They are primarily used to put things together (e.g., hammers and nail guns) or to take them apart (e.g., jackhammers and saws). Tools are often classified as **hand tools** and **power tools (Fig. 2)**. Hand tools include all non-powered tools, such as hammers and pliers. Power tools are divided into classes, depending on the power source: electrical tools (powered by electricity), pneumatic tools (powered by compressed air), liquid-fuel tools (usually powered by gasoline), powder-actuated tools (usually powered by an explosive and operated like a gun) and hydraulic tools (powered by pressure from a liquid).

Fig. 2. Some hand and power tools. Source: True Value (2020)

3.1 Some common Tools in Agricultural Mechanization Workshop

The basic hand tools for agriculture: picks, shovels and spades, forks, hoes, hand operated sprayers, small hand tools, simple power tools, harvest tools, wheelbarrows, etc. These tools are used for making farm work easy. Most of them are manually used (Ajibola, 2019). The ones used in the agricultural mechanization workshop include: basic tools for metal cutting, basic striking tools, punches, taps and dies, power tools, portable pneumatic power tools, screw and tap extractors, pipe and tube cutters and flaring tools, screw drivers, etc. Their functions are briefly described below.

Basic tools for metal cutting: snips and shears, hacksaws, chisels, files, twist drills, wrenches (open-end, box-end, combination, box, socket, torque, adjustable, union nut, adjustable pipe,

spanner, strap, setscrew – Allen & Bristol,), ratchet, handles (hinged, sliding T-bar, speed, socket), pliers (slip-joint, wrench, nose, combination, side-cutting, curved-needle, diagonal, duckbill, water-pump, groove-joint, wire-twister). Most of the engineering components such as gears, bearings, clutches, tools, screws and nuts etc. need dimensional accuracy and good surface finish for serving their purposes (Gunasegaran, 2018). That is the essence of these tools.

Basic striking tools: machinists' hammers (ball peen, straight peen, cross peen, soft metal or plastic, plain faced claw, riveting, bell-faced claw), mallets (carpenter's, rawhide, rawhide-faced, wooden, rubber), sledges (double face, cross peen, screwed-in inserted plastic face). Striking tools refer to tools that are used to strike or hit various objects, and they include hammers, chisels, punches, and drifts. Some of these striking tools are used with attachment devices such as nails and rivets (Washmuth, 2022).

Punches: a hand punch is a steel tool that is held in the hand and struck on one end with a hammer. There are several types: pin, center, prick, drift or starting, aligning, hollow shank gasket. Fourier and Fournier (1989) defined a punch is a tool used to indent or create a hole through a hard surface. They usually consist of a hard metal rod with a narrow tip at one end and a broad flat "butt" at the other. When used, the narrower end is pointed against a target surface and the broad end is then struck with a hammer or mallet, causing the blunt force of the blow to be transmitted down the rod body and focused more sharply onto a small area. Punches are used also to mark holes that are used as a guide for drilling.

Taps and dies: Taps and dies are used to cut threads in metal, plastics, or hard rubber. The taps are used for cutting internal threads, and the dies are used to cut external threads. There are many different types of taps. However, the most common are the taper, plug, bottoming, and pipe taps. For dies: there are the solid (square pipe, the rethreading), adjustable (open, screw, two-piece collet, two-piece rectangular pipe, round-split). Associate with these are the diestocks, die-collet, and tap wrenches, the adjustable die guide and ratchet diestocks as well as the tap and die thread sets (Keenan, 2005).

Power tools include: portable electric drills, three-jaw chuck and chuck key, portable grinder, electric disk sanders, portable electric sander, reversible electric impact wrench. A power tool is a tool that is actuated by an additional power source and mechanism other than the solely manual labor used with hand tools. The most common types of power tools use electric motors. Internal combustion engines and compressed air are also commonly used (*Nagyszalanczy, 2001*).

Portable pneumatic power tools: pneumatic chipping hammer, rotary impact scaler, rotary and needle scalers, rotary scaling and chipping tool, needle impact scaler, portable pneumatic impact wrench. These tools are powered by compressed air supplied by an air compressor. Pneumatic tools can also be driven by compressed carbon dioxide (CO₂) stored in small cylinders allowing for portability (Majumder, 1996).

Screw and tap extractors are used to remove screws and taps without damaging the surrounding materials. There are the straight tap and the spiral screw extractors (Gilles, 2003). Tap extractors are used to extract taps of different sizes; these sets include multiple extractors. Fingers on the extractor grip the flutes on a broken tap. They are used with a tap wrench to remove taps with straight flutes from the work piece.

Pipe and tubing cutters and flaring tools: pipe cutters are used to cut pipe made of steel, brass, copper, wrought iron, or lead; tubing cutters are used to cut tubing made of iron, steel, brass, copper, or aluminum, while flaring tools are used to make flares in the ends of tubing (single, double – die block, handle, adaptors. Pipe and tube cutters are hand-held tools or machines that use a rotating cutting wheel, blade, or other tool head to separate a long piece of tubular material into two or more parts. Pipe and tube cutters can be manually, electrically, pneumatically, or hydraulically powered. The type of cutter used depends on the material, diameter, and thickness of the pipe or tube (**RS Components, 2012**).

A **screwdriver** is one of the most basic of hand tools. It is also the most frequently abused of all hand tools. It is designed for one function only—to drive and to remove screws. There are many types: heavy duty, clutch tip, reed and prince, phillips head, torque-set, offset, ratchet and spiral. A screwdriver is classified by its tip, which is shaped to fit the driving surfaces—slots, grooves, recesses, etc.—on the corresponding screw head. Proper use requires that the screwdriver's tip engage the head of a screw of the same size and type designation as the screwdriver tip (*Encyclopedia Britannica, 2013*).

4. TOOL WORK HABITS AND WORK ETHICS

As a workshop/laboratory technician or technologist or craftsman, there are certain ethics that must be followed concerning tools/equipment, even before you select them. The efficiency of craftsmen and the tools they use are determined to a great extent by the way they keep their tools. Safe and proper storage of tools define tool work habit, while appropriate behavior in the workplace define work ethics.

- A. Tool work habit has to do with “having a place for every tool, and keeping every tool in its place” (Gleen. 2014; True Value, 2020).
 1. Keep each tool/equipment in its proper stowage place – specialized toolboxes or pouches inside the tool room within the work station/center or workshop/laboratory.
 2. Keep all tools in good condition – to protect them from rust, nicks, burrs, and breakage. Apply a light film of oil after cleaning to prevent rust on tools.
 3. Keep tool allowance complete – when issued a toolbox, each tool should be placed in it when not in use. When the toolbox is not actually at the work site, it should be locked and stored in a designated area. An inventory list is kept in each toolbox to be used to account for the tools before and after use to prevent loss.
 4. Use each tool for the job it was designated to do - each particular type of tool has a specific purpose. Using the wrong tool and improper use of tools when performing maintenance or repairs, may result in improper maintenance and cause damage to the equipment being worked on or damage the tool itself and even cause injury or death.
 5. Safe maintenance practices - always avoid placing tools on or above machinery or an electrical apparatus. Never leave tools unattended where machinery or engines are running.
 6. Never use damaged tools - a battered screwdriver may slip and spoil the screw slot, damage other parts, or cause painful injury. A gauge strained out of shape will result in inaccurate measurements.
 7. Always keep hand tools clean and free from dirt, grease, and foreign matter. Oily, dirty, and greasy tools are slippery and dangerous to use. After use, return tools promptly to their proper place in the toolbox or on the rack.

Improve your own efficiency by organizing your tools so that those used most frequently can be reached easily without digging through the entire contents of the box. Avoid accumulating unnecessary junk.

B. Work ethic is a belief that work and diligence have a moral benefit and an inherent ability, virtue or value to strengthen character and individual abilities (Marek et al., 2014). Good work ethics is a tool that helps one become a valuable asset to an organization, which according to Gopakumar (2020) and Cruz (2022) include the following:

1. Punctuality – This one holds really high among necessary ethics at a workplace. It is said that 90% of success is showing up. Employee tardiness takes a toll not just on productivity but also on workplace morale signaling lack of commitment. Employees need to schedule their travel, meetings, deadlines etc. to be in the best practice of punctuality thereby minimizing bad elements like procrastination, delays and thereby increasing quality time spent at work.
2. Focus – Staying focused at the task in hand is one of the greatest challenges employees seem to face in today's work environment especially when you have endless distractions around. Gossiping employees, cell phones, stress and fatigue, not prioritizing tasks are all a few examples of how one can easily lose focus at work. It is imperative to understand these situations and work hard on bringing back focus on priorities so as to end the day constructively. Manage time for a healthy work life balance.
3. Dedication – Dedication and staying focused sort of works hand in hand. You need to stay focused in order to be dedicated to the work you're carrying out. Staying dedicated for a day keeps you on the right track, upholding the dedication for weeks and months puts you on the track for prolonged success in that it leaves you disciplined and resilient in the face of any obstacles in your way. You're left with a sense of ownership which level once reached enables you to carry the task at hand to fruition.
4. Professionalism – One of the most important qualities is how to be a thorough professional. It shows a great deal about how serious an employee treats his work to be. It is about being capable of seeing the bigger picture, realizing the greater benefits of work, being a team player rather than being individualistic, being responsible for one's actions, staying positive in times of difficulties and doing their job to the best of their abilities.
5. Personal improvement – A good employee is one who constantly upgrades and updates himself striving to be better than he was yesterday. An incessant hunger and a diehard passion drive him to excel not just at work but generally in life. Monotony tends to kill the growth drive in an employee and once this negative development begins to take form it leads to stagnation which is unpleasant. Therefore, a constant undying desire to improve helps a great deal in remaining focused and dedicated. Ask relevant questions when in doubt.
6. Initiative – Successful employees and great leaders are the ones who take initiatives and act on them. The ability to act independently is a crucial element of having a good work ethic —no matter how talented someone is if they need to be micro-managed, they'll hold your team back.

7. Productivity – Maintaining all the above qualities would be of no use if ultimately the numbers don't show qualitatively and quantitatively, which all boils down to the term 'productivity'. All that matters to an organization at the end of it is its productivity which decides the results and profits for the organization. Candidates with a good work ethic find a way to get the job done, no matter the challenge, no matter how they are feeling that day.
8. Respect and achieve deadlines. Sticking to **deadlines** is a positive habit and trademark of successful people. Completing work on time shows that you're accountable and can nail tasks efficiently. Say no to procrastination.
9. Take criticism well. Don't frown at every criticism that comes your way. No one is perfect. Giving or receiving negative feedback is important for growth, and it's something you need from time to time. You should treat your employer as your career coach and learn to de-personalize the message. The feedback from an employee or your boss is to help you focus and become a better version of yourself.
10. Use a habit management app such as ClickUp. ClickUp is one of the most popular and highest-rated habit management apps used by productive teams across all domains. It's an all-in-one app that lets you set, manage, and track your personal projects and professional goals with ease.

4.1 Safe Handling of Tools

Craftsmen/technicians/technologists should be knowledgeable on safe procedures for working with tools. Tools can pose a safety risk when they are misplaced or improperly handled by workers. Some of the precautions to be taken when handling tools are, according to Crosbie (2020):

1. Workers should never carry tools up or down a ladder in a way that inhibits grip. Ideally, tools should be hoisted up and down using a bucket or strong bag, rather than being carried by the worker.
2. Tools should always be carefully handed from one employee to another – never tossed. Pointed tools should be passed either in their carrier or with the handles toward the receiver.
3. Workers carrying large tools or equipment on their shoulders should pay close attention to clearances when turning and maneuvering around the workplace.
4. Pointed tools such as chisels and screwdrivers should never be carried in a worker's pocket. Acceptable ways to carry them include in a toolbox, pointed down in a tool belt or pocket tool pouch, or in the hand with the tip always held away from the body.
5. Tools should always be put away when not in use. Leaving tools lying around on an elevated structure such as a scaffold poses a significant risk to workers below. This risk increases in areas with heavy vibration.
6. Wrong tool or poorly maintained tool should not be used for any job. Dull tools can make the work much harder, require more force and result in more injuries.
7. Defective tools should be taken out of service immediately and tagged or locked out to make sure no one else uses them until they are fixed.

4.2 Safety Challenges in Handling different Tools

Hand tools include a wide range of tools, from axes to wrenches. Eye injuries are very common from the use of hand tools, as a piece of wood or metal can fly off and lodge in the eye (Lockwood, 2021). The size of the tool is important: some women and men with relatively small hands have difficulty with large tools (Nagourney, 2008). A chisel with a mushroomed head might shatter on impact and send fragments flying. Cutting material at an awkward angle can result in a loss of balance and an injury. In addition, hand tools can produce sparks that can ignite explosions if the work is being done around flammable liquids or vapors. In such cases, spark-resistant tools, such as those made from brass or aluminum, are needed.

Power tools are more dangerous than hand tools, because of the increased power of the tool (Gibadi,, 2022) The biggest dangers from power tools are from accidental start-up and slipping or losing one's balance during use. The power source itself can cause injuries or death, for example, through electrocution with electrical tools or gasoline explosions from liquid-fuel tools (Elcosh, 2002). Most power tools have a guard, in proper working order and not overridden, to protect the moving parts while the tool is not in operation. A portable circular saw, for example, should have an upper guard covering the top half of the blade and an automatic-return retractable lower guard which covers the teeth while the saw is not operating and cover the lower half of the blade when the tool has finished working. Power tools often also have safety switches that shut off the tool as soon as a switch is released or have catches that must be engaged before the tool can operate (Nagyszalanczy, 2001).

One of the main hazards of **electrical tools** is the risk of electrocution (Tajuddin, 2019). A frayed wire or a tool that does not have a ground (that directs the electrical circuit to the ground in an emergency) can result in electricity running through the body and death by electrocution. This can be prevented by:

- (a) using double-insulated tools (insulated wires in an insulated housing),
- (b) using grounded tools and ground-fault circuit interrupters (which will detect a leak of electricity from a wire and automatically shut off the tool);
- (c) by never using electrical tools in damp or wet locations; and
- (d) by wearing insulated gloves and safety footwear.
- (e) Power cords have to be protected from abuse and damage.

Other types of power tools include powered abrasive-wheel tools, like grinding, cutting or buffing wheels, which present the risk of flying fragments coming off the wheel. The wheel should be tested to make sure it is not cracked and will not fly apart during use. It should spin freely on its spindle. The user should never stand directly in front of the wheel during start-up, in case it breaks. Eye protection is essential when using these tools.

Pneumatic tools include chippers, drills, hammers and sanders that shoot fasteners at high speed and pressure into surfaces. These tools, otherwise known as air tools, are powered by compressed air and can be used in a variety of applications. While these powered tools are efficient and effective, there are several things to consider when it comes to the safe and proper handling of your pneumatic tools. If the object being fastened is thin, the fastener may go through it and strike someone at a distance. This results in the risk of shooting fasteners into the user or others (Butler, 2020). Pneumatic tools can also be noisy and cause hearing loss. Air

hoses should be well connected before use to prevent them from disconnecting and whipping around and should be protected from abuse and damage. Compressed-air guns should never be pointed at anyone or against oneself. Eye, face and hearing protection are required when using these tools. Jack hammer users should also wear foot protection in case these heavy tools are dropped (Butler, 2020).

Gas-powered tools are usually operated with gasoline. The most serious hazard associated with the use of fuel-powered tools comes from fuel vapors that can burn or explode and also give off dangerous exhaust fumes. The fuel explosion hazards occurs particularly during filling. They should be filled only after they have been shut down and allowed to cool off. Proper ventilation must be provided if they are being filled in a closed space. Using these tools in a closed space can also cause problems from carbon monoxide exposure (States and McQuaid, 2022).

Powder-actuated tools are like loaded guns and should be operated only by specially trained personnel. They should never be loaded until immediately before use and should never be left loaded and unattended. Firing requires two motions: bringing the tool into position and pulling the trigger. Powder-actuated tools, which should not be used in explosive atmospheres, require sufficient pressure against the surface before they can be fired. If the muzzle is not pressed against a surface with sufficient force, the firing pin is blocked and cannot reach the load to fire it. They should never be pointed at anyone and should be inspected before each use (Krueger, 2021). These tools should have a safety shield at the end of the muzzle to prevent the release of flying fragments during firing. Power tools present a considerable vibration, sprains and strains hazards to workers as in the chain-saw vibration. Tools where vibration has been dampened or reduced should be purchased.

Hydraulic power tools should use a fire-resistant fluid and be operated under safe pressures. A jack should have a safety mechanism to prevent it from being jacked up too high and should display its load limit prominently. Jacks have to be set up on a level surface, centered, bear against a level surface and apply force evenly to be used safely (Student Lesson, 2022).

Poorly designed tools can also contribute to fatigue from awkward postures or grips, which, in turn, can also lead to accidents. Many tools are not designed for use by left-handed workers or individuals with small hands. Use of gloves can make it harder to grip a tool properly and requires tighter gripping of power tools, which can result in excessive fatigue. Use of tools by craftsmen/technicians for repetitive jobs can lead to cumulative trauma disorders, like carpal tunnel syndrome or tendinitis. Safety Stage (2022) admonished technicians/technologists about using the right tool for the job and choosing tools with the best design features that feel most comfortable in the hand while working. This can assist in avoiding these problems, and make the work easier, safer and more efficient.

5. TOOL MAINTENANCE POLICY

Tools in the initial days always perform to their fullest capacity but as time goes with regular wear and tear, this becomes increasingly difficult. With proper and regular maintenance tool work capacity can be maintained at a more or less same level. Tools have always been the most crucial asset for workers. These are the tools that make your job possible. In return, you remain in debt to protect and maintain these tools, as maintenance and protection of the tools make them serve you for a longer time (Marsigroup, 2020). Maintenance at times requires replacement

decisions whereby existing tool is replaced with a new one, which may enhance features capable of performing similar function. The need for replacement may arise because of normal use, obsolescence, early service failure, destruction, etc. Maintenance is defined as a process in which working condition of a tool/equipment is maintained at the optimum level as to give maximum output. Maintenance is done through repair, partial replacement and total replacement. Maintenance, therefore, is a very important workshop ethics. And any workshop should have a maintenance policy. Maintenance policy *ensures that equipment are always in ready and reliable condition (MSG, 2015)*. Following is the significance of the maintenance policy: it ensures that

1. Tools are always in ready and reliable condition.
2. Tools are always calibrated to provide good-quality services
3. There are no major breakdowns.

If an effective maintenance policy is not implemented, then the following results:

1. Full capacity utilization may not be achieved.
2. Increase in production cost as fixed labor cost cannot be reduced.
3. Increase in maintenance cost as more spare parts are required.
4. Reduction in product quality and increase in wastage.
5. Safety of workers and operators in jeopardy.

However, maintenance should be planned with the following key points:

1. Identify the tools/equipment for maintenance and technique for the maintenance.
2. Categorize maintenance into routine, priority and emergency.
3. Plan maintenance considering cost, time, space, etc.
4. Material planning for maintenance requirements.
5. Budget time and money requirements.

The need to schedule maintenance can be best described as follows:

1. To optimize usage of plant, machinery and tools.
2. To optimize usage of manpower in maintenance.
3. To ensure smooth production flow.

From above it is safe to posit that it is very critical and important for any workshop/laboratory to have a robust and effective maintenance and repair policy as part of its workshop ethics.

5.1 Inspect (and repair) Tools every time they are used

In a typical workshop, it is important to take time to inspect the tools every time they are to be used to ensure not only user safety while using them, but the longevity of the tools as well. In so doing, Simon (2018) suggested we look out for the following:

1. **Loose, cracked, or splintered handle** is prone to breaking during use, which can cause injury to you or others. If the handle is cracked or heavily splintered, you'll need to replace it.

- 2. Mushroomed heads on tools like chisels and wedges** could shatter on impact when in use. Fortunately, this problem can be solved by keeping the tools sharpened. Plan to sharpen them every six months or so just as a habit or as soon as mushroomed heads are noticed.
- 3. Corrosion and rust.** Depending on the level of corrosion or rust, the tool may be unsafe to use. Try removing the rust or just replacing the tool. Removing rust from tools is actually pretty easy if the damage isn't too great.
- 4. Cracked housing on power tools.** If a power tool has anything more than a simple hairline crack on the housing, don't use it. Get it repaired by a professional before use.
- 5. Power tools that don't start easily** should not be used. Take the time to clean and lubricate it and if that doesn't solve the problem, get it repaired by a professional.
- 6. Frayed insulation or exposed wires are** obviously electrical hazards. While some electrical tape might take care of a small problem temporarily, it's best to have the tool repaired before using it.

5.2 Tool Safety

Good tools are an asset in any workshop and can be quite an investment, but they have to be taken good care of. Keeping the tools properly stored, cleaned, and maintained will save time and money. High point of tool safety is its storage which is a key workshop ethics (Newswise, 2011). Several tool storage options are safe and easy to use, allowing you to customize your tools and equipment to best fit your needs. No matter which tool storage option you choose, the important thing is providing a protected environment for the equipment (Frost, 2022). Tools must be stored properly working with the space available. They may be hung on pegboards, stored in boxes, bags, or chests, or may be kept in drawers or on shelves in the workshop. Improve your own efficiency by organizing your tools so that those used most frequently can be reached easily without digging through the entire contents of the box (Frost, 2022). Peg boards make a great storage system for tools as they let all the tools be seen at a glance and they can make use of wall space in a pretty efficient way. With insufficient wall space though, advantage can still be taken of peg boards by building a hinged system, a rolling peg board, or even a portable peg board storage system (Puisis, 2022) or use made of the flip board system. The portability of tool boxes makes for great tool storage. However, some people opt to store all their tools in tool boxes, but for most, the tool box is a way of carrying around the most-used tools while leaving the bulk safely stored on peg boards, shelves, or drawers.

Rust is public enemy number one when it comes to tools. To avoid rust when storing the tools CF-T (2022) made the following suggestions among others:

- 1. Keep tools in a dry place** and avoid humid spaces.
- 2. Hang the tools** so that they don't rest on the floor. Moisture can easily creep up from concrete floors.
- 3. Store power tools in their original cases** unless you have a climate-controlled workshop. It's best to store power tools in the hard plastic cases they usually come with. Not only are they better-protected from humidity, they're just better-protected in general.

4. **Use silica gel packs or rust collector** that come in lots of packaging to keep moisture at bay. Toss them in drawers or toolboxes and they can help keep rust away. You can also buy rust inhibitors for the same purpose and even anti-rust liners for drawers and shelves.

As it is said, cleanliness is next to godliness, so it is with tools. Cleaning the tools after the day's work is essential for keeping them in good shape. Cleaning the tools doesn't have to be difficult at all if well prepared:

1. **Hand tools:** You can clean most hand tools by simply wiping them down with a rag. If they're dirty, don't be afraid to give them a good wash with soap and water and wipe with a clean rag. Wipe wooden handles with a rag dampened with a little linseed oil.
2. **Power tools:** Power tools are a little trickier to clean. First, make sure the tool is unplugged before cleaning it. Next, get all the dust off using an air compressor. Wipe down the surface of the tool and then lubricate any moving parts. Machine oil is a fine choice for this. However, check the manual that came with the tool to see if they have better recommendations.

Don't forget that the toolboxes, belts, and bags will need some care as well. Clean out the toolboxes every once in a while by emptying them and wiping them and condition the leather once in a while. For bags and belts not made of leather, a quick wash should do the trick.

6. PERSONAL SAFETY EQUIPMENT/PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT (PSE/PPE)

Personal protective equipment (PPE) is protective clothing, helmets, goggles, or other garments or equipment designed to protect the wearer's body from injury or infection. The hazards addressed by protective equipment include physical, electrical, heat, chemicals, biohazards, and airborne particulate matter (Citation, 2012). Some of these are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Some personal protective equipment or Personal Safety Equipment (PPE/PSE) (Szawlowski, 2019).

Personal protective equipment/personal safety equipment (PPE/PSE) is defined as “all equipment (including clothing affording protection against the weather) which is intended to be worn or held by a person at work and which protects them against one or more risks to their health or safety” (Szawłowski, 2019). The tools/equipment in all workshops and laboratories and their use and misuse pose risks on the workers/employee, the environment and the tools/equipment. The risks may arise from biological, chemical, environmental and physical processes: radiation, UV light, X-rays; chemicals, biological agents; lifting, pushing, pulling; cold, wet, heat; noise; equipment hazards and general hazards. And there is the need for control measures by the use of gloves, footwear, respiratory protective equipment (RPE), eye/face masks/shields, hearing gear, body/head protectors and others. It is important that wear PPE/PSE all the time workers are exposed to risk.

6.1 General Body Protections

Different parts of the worker’s body should be protected when working in a laboratory/workshop: hands, feet, eyes, stomach, etc.

Gloves (Fig. 4) should be worn when handling: hazardous materials; toxic chemicals; corrosive materials; materials with sharp or rough edges; and very hot or very cold materials, as well as rough, scaly, or splintery objects. Special flameproof gloves are used for gas and electric-arc welding because of sparks and other hot flying objects. Electricians are usually required to wear insulating rubber gloves. Gloves are a kind of second skin that allows them to handle hazardous materials, chemicals, and tools without sacrificing the dexterity they need to perform their work skillfully (Fontaine, 2021).

Fig. 4. Hand protection glove (Szawłowski, 2019).

Safety shoes/boots are important in the workplace for: protection against falling objects, prevention of slips and falls, help posture and prevent muscle strain, protection against the elements, and help protect against electric shocks (Heath Brook, 2022). The ones with steel plate placed in the toe area prevent damage to the toes from falling objects. Other safety shoes are designed for use where danger from sparking could cause an explosion with rubber soles and non-metallic eyelets and nails.

Goggle is for proper eye protection. Eye protection is necessary because of hazards posed by infrared and ultraviolet radiation, or by flying objects such as sparks, globules of molten metal, or chipped concrete and wood. These hazards are ever-present during chipping, grinding, welding, cutting, soldering, and a variety of other operations. It is absolutely necessary to use eye protection devices, such as goggles, helmets, and face shields during eye-hazard operations. Some goggles have plastic lenses that resist shattering upon impact and others have appropriate filter lenses to limit harmful infrared and ultraviolet radiation from arcs or flames (Tajuddin, 2021).

The safety strap and body belt are called extra hands when one works aloft. The body belt, strapped around your waist, contains various pockets for small tools. The safety strap is a leather or neoprene-impregnated nylon belt with a tongue-type buckle at each end. While you are climbing you will have the safety strap hanging by both ends from the left ring (called a D-ring because of its shape) on the body belt. When you are at working position, you unstrap one end of the safety strap, pass it around the supporting structure so there is no danger of its slipping (at least 18 inches from the top of the part on which it is fastened), and hook it to the right D-ring on the body belt (Workplace, 2022).

6.2 Respiratory Protective Equipment (RPE) (Fig. 5)

Respiratory Protective Equipment (RPE) is a particular type of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), used to protect the individual wearer against the inhalation of hazardous substances in the workplace air (HSA, 2022).

Fig.5. Some respiratory protective equipment (RPE) (Szawlowski, 2019).

Respiratory protection may be required against poisonous gases, vapors and fumes, dusts and aerosols, and biological agents, etc. RPE, which provides absolute protection against a respiratory hazard, must be selected carefully to ensure it gives adequate, if not absolute, protection depending on the toxicity of the agent, the size of the particle, the amount of movement involved in the task and working conditions, the worker's face shape, presence of beard, glasses etc. and the Workplace Exposure Limit (WEL) of the substance and contaminant levels (HSA, 2022).

RPE consists of two (2) major categories: respirators (air purifying) which filter contaminated air (simple filtering and powered) and breathing apparatus or equipment that provides clean air from independent external or outside source (air supplied) (simple compressed-air apparatus, fresh air hose equipment and breathing apparatus) (HSA, 2022). There are several types of RPE as shown below (Putter, 2021):

Paper filters which cover chin, nose and mouth only protects against dust particles and not against vapors and gases.

Disposable half mask containing both gas and dust particle filtering elements protects against dust particles and certain types and quantities of gases and vapors.

Half mask covering chin, mouth and nose made of silicon or rubber with replaceable parts to protect against dust and gas hazards.

Full mask covering all the face made of silicon or rubber with replaceable parts protects against dust and gas hazards.

Positive full face hood/helmet protects against dust particles and certain gas and vapor hazards.

Power assisted full face mask respirator protects against both particulate and gas/vapor hazards.

6.2.1 Use and maintenance of RPE

All masks must be face fitted by appropriately trained personnel, while the wearer must be trained on how to use and maintain them. Maintenance is a requirement for all RPE, except for disposable (single use) RPE, and should be carried out by properly trained personnel. The masks must be inspected thoroughly before use and on regular basis of not more than once a month. Selected RPE has to offer an adequate protection to the hazard and to reduce exposure to the level required to preserve the wearer's health. Furthermore, the RPE has to be suitable for the wearer, task and environment, in such a way that the wearer can work freely and without additional risks due to the use of RPE (HSE, 2013). Therefore, RPE must be adequate and suitable. Not wearing the correct RPE can result in ill health, and in some environments, such as confined spaces, it can be lethal to workers if there is toxic gases or oxygen depletion (Putter, 2021).

6.3 Eyes and Face Protection (Fig. 6)

If you are exposed to dust, acids, molten metal's, grinding wheels, hazardous optical radiation – you need to take the proper precautions and protect your eyes. If you don't, it's possible to lose the precious gift of sight.

Fig. 6. Some eye and face protection (Szawlowski, 2019).

According to Owczarek (2022), each type of individual protection PPE is made to protect our eyes from contact with something that we call a harmful or dangerous factor. Examples of these factors are: Impact (e.g. fragments of solid bodies), Optical radiation (e.g. radiation related to welding processes, sunglare, laser radiation, , ionizing radiation, UV), Dusts and gases (e.g. coal dust welding fumes or aerosols of harmful chemical substances), Droplets and splashes of fluids

(e.g. splatters appearing while pouring fluids), Melted metals and hot solid bodies (e.g. chips of melted metals appearing in metallurgical processes), Electric arc (e.g. occurring while conducting high-tension works, sparks, etc.). To protect eyes against these harmful or dangerous factors, they come as Spectacles; Protective goggles; Face shields; Welder's face shields (this category of eye protection includes hand screens, face screens, goggles and hoods) (Owczarek, 2022).

6.4 Hearing Protection (Fig. 7)

Noise is a serious problem in some industrial workshops. Hearing protectors are required to prevent noise-induced hearing loss. Hearing protection devices reduce the noise energy reaching and causing damage to the inner ear. Occupational hearing loss is one of the most pervasive problems in today's occupational environment, affecting workers in manufacturing, construction, transportation, agriculture, and the military (Franks *et al.*, 1996).

Fig. 7. Hearing protection (Szawlowski, 2019).

Risk from noise which can cause temporary or permanent deafness may arise if there is constant noise above 80db for an 8 hour work period; impact noise; and explosive noise (EHS, 2022). Ear protection comes in the form of:

Ear plugs - which fit inside the ear canal, may not be suitable for people with a history of ear problems.

Canal caps - soft rubber caps attached to a headband which presses them into the openings of the ear canal.

Ear muffs – hard plastic cups with sound absorbent filling which fit over the ears and are sealed to the head by cushions. They are pressed to the head by means of a head band or some special fittings attached to some types of safety helmet.

6.5 Foot Protection (Fig. 8)

Foot protection is any piece of personal protective equipment (PPE) protecting one's foot from any injury while at work or during movement. The foot is a vital part of our body and since we are on our feet constantly from day to day, they are more susceptible to injury. If a foot is injured, our movement may be temporarily or permanently restricted (Safeopedia. 2018)

Fig. 8. Foot protection (Szawlowski, 2019).

Where there the risk of crush or impact injuries; chemical or molten metal burns; contamination with harmful substances; penetration with sharp objects e.g. glass; or slipping, an appropriate safety footwear should be put on. On slippery floors workers should put on anti-slip footwear and steel toe-capped boots if there is likelihood of crush or impact injuries. According to EHS (2022a), foot and leg protection choices include the following:

- Safety-toed shoes or boots protect against falling, crushing or rolling hazards. Safety-toed footwear must meet the minimum compression and impact performance standards in ANSI Z41-1999 or provide equivalent protection.
- Some safety shoes may be designed to be electrically conductive to prevent the buildup of static electricity in areas with the potential for explosive atmospheres or nonconductive to protect workers from workplace electrical hazards.
- Metatarsal guards protect the instep area from impact and compression. Made of aluminum, steel, fiber or plastic, these guards may be strapped to the outside of regular work shoes.
- Toe guards fit over the toes of regular shoes to protect the toes from impact and compression hazards. They may be made of steel, aluminum, or plastic.
- Rubber overshoes are used for concrete work and areas where flooding is a concern
- Shoes with slip-resistant soles are required for certain departments and should be used in areas where slips and falls on wet floors are most likely.
- Studded treads and overshoes should be used when employees must work on ice or snow-covered walking surfaces.
- Leggings protect the lower legs and feet from heat hazards such as molten metal or welding sparks. Safety snaps allow leggings to be removed quickly.

6.6 Head Protection (Fig. 9)

Head protection is required when working in an area with the potential of an object falling and hitting the head or when there is a significant electrical shock exposure to the head. Head protection is an item of personal protective equipment (PPE), which is generally designed to protect the scalp area and sometimes the jaw as well and protects these areas from impact trauma and burns (Safeopedia, 2018a).

Fig. 9. Head protection (Szawlowski, 2019).

Head protection includes: industrial safety helmets; scalp protectors (bump caps); and caps, hairnets etc. Head protection should: be of an appropriate shell size for the wearer; and have an easily adjustable headband, nape and chin strap.

6.7 Body protection clothing (Fig. 10)

Protective clothing is any clothing specifically designed, treated or fabricated to protect personnel from hazards that are caused by extreme environmental conditions, or a dangerous work environment (Safeopedia, 2018b).

Fig. 10. Body protection (Szawlowski, 2019).

Protective clothing including standard lab coats, over coats or aprons should be worn to protect against: hazardous substances; machinery parts; and extreme conditions. Loose clothing must not be worn near machinery due to the risk of it become trapped by moving parts. Body protection should be washed regularly. Barrier creams may also be used as a form of body protection. These include: sunscreens to protect parts of your body from UV radiation that are not easily protected by clothes and thus protect against subsequent skin cancer when working outdoors or on field trips; hand creams to be used when wearing gloves for long periods of time which reduce the chances of developing contact dermatitis; where workers have to frequently wash their hands.

6.8 Guidelines for human and machine safety in workshop

Safety, according to Bello (2012), is a state of being at little or no risk of injury resulting from a harmful external impact, inhalation, or contact. Safety in any work environment hinges on prevention and mitigation of harm which is approached using three (3) steps of **Recognition**: Identify hazards to which a person at the workplace is likely to be exposed; **Evaluation**: Assess the risk of injury or harm to a person resulting from each hazard; and **Control**: Consider the means by which the risk may be reduced. In all these, it is the human person that mitigates or prevents harm and any human error causes accident. Therefore, the technologist or technician or craftsman in the workshop has the responsibility to eliminate or minimize errors to the barest minimum for safety in the workplace.

Injuries occur when workers are:

- a) not paying close attention (or are indifference) to work, or
- b) when the operator lost concentration or forgot something and was not paying close attention,
- c) when he/she took a risk, ignored a warning or
- d) when he/she failed to follow safety rules.

Workshop safety rules include the following (StopLearn, 2022):

1. Wear industrial protective clothing coat or apron.
2. Wear protective pair of shoes with strong toe caps.
3. Do not carry sharp tools in your pockets. Put them on a tool rack.

4. Keep tools in the locker after use.
5. Keep your sharp tools in a safe place.
6. Do not use chisels or file without handles.
7. Give out chisel and other sharp edged tools by the handle.
8. Keep your hand behind the cutting edge of chisel when using it for cutting.
9. Select the right tools for the job.
10. Wear goggles or eye shield while griddling your tools.
11. Do not fiddle with the 'on' and 'off' switches of the machine and appliance.
12. Do not run around in the workshop.
13. Do not make alarming noise in the workshop.
14. Do not operate a machine, unless you have been taught its working operation, and obtained permission before use.
15. Give the machine your undivided attention during operation.
16. Start and wait until a machine gathers its operating speed before use.
17. Stop the machine after operation.
18. Do not overload a machine.
19. Do not allow the workshop floor to become slippery.
20. Report any injury no matter how small.
21. Ask for the first aid treatment when necessary.

Employers have a duty to minimize the risk of injury at their workplace by ensuring a safe work environment through inductions, training and re-training.

7. CONCLUSION

This reviewed paper has tried to highlight the importance of workshop ethics: selection and handling of laboratory/workshop tools and equipment. It has looked at the purpose and function of safety; selection of tools/equipment; tool work habit, work ethics and tool management policy; the importance of wearing and caring of PPE; the use and maintenance of RPE. All for the purpose of running a safe workshop/laboratory.

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